

QUALITIES OF STRENGTH AND SPEED OF JUDOKERS AND POSSIBILITIES OF THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. Judo is an excellent tool for developing physical fitness, coordination and mental endurance in young athletes. Judo is an effective sport for students to improve their physical and mental well-being, develop agility and strength qualities, and this has a positive effect on their academic and personal success.

Key words: physical quality, speed, general strength, special strength, absolute strength, relative strength, quick strength, explosive strength, strength endurance.

The physical fitness of a judoka is considered one of the important components of sports training and is a process aimed at developing physical qualities - strength, endurance, flexibility, agility, and agility.

The main tasks of physical training are as follows:

The level of health of athletes and their organism increase the functionality of various systems.

The development of physical qualities in a unit that meets the peculiarity of sports wrestling.

Physical fitness is divided into general, auxiliary and special training.

The general physical fitness of the judoka is the foundation, the necessary basis for achieving high results. It mainly ensures the resolution of the following tasks:

The comprehensive harmonic development of the body of a judoka, increasing its functionality, developing its physical qualities.

Increase the level of health.

The correct use of active rest during the period of intense training and competition nagruzkas.

General physical fitness involves the accumulation of various tools. Among them are exercises performed on projectiles and with projectiles, exercises performed on a special track with a partner, other sports: acrobatics, athletics, sports games, swimming and x.k.general developmental exercises derived from are distinguished.

Physical training is designed to create a special basis necessary for the effective execution of a large-scale work aimed at the development of special movement skills. It has a much narrower and more specific direction and solves the following tasks:

Mainly to develop qualities that are more typical for the fight.

Selective development of muscle groups involved to a large extent in wrestler movements.

As advanced means of auxiliary physical training, such exercises are used that are suitable for the main actions that the wrestler performs in competition activities, due to their kinematic and dynamic composition and the nature of neuromuscular tension. Among such exercises, the following can be distinguished: performing various methods of wrestling by pointing; exercises performed on special trainer devices; exercises with a wrestler's mannequin.

The special physical training of the wrestler is aimed at the development of the qualities of movement in strict accordance with the requirements imposed by the features of the wrestlers' competition activities.

Special physical training of wrestlers is carried out mainly on the wrestling carpet and is aimed at developing the most important qualities of movement in the composition of the movement qualifications. Therefore, as the main tools of special physical training, involving various possible complexities, kilgan holdamusabac exercises are considered. Such complex exercises enhance the effect on the wrestler's body. For example, throwing a partner in the ogirrok weight class, in the position where the partners are replaced, training contests are performed, and x.k. This all-in-one exercise provides the opportunity to develop one or another mechanism of energy supply, shows complex holddata to the training of the wrestler, simultaneously increasing his physical and technical-tactical training.

All indicated types of physical fitness are inextricably linked with each other. Not giving enough happiness to any type of physical fitness during the training process will end up full of an increase in the level of sports performance. Therefore, it is very difficult to adhere to the optimal ratio of the types of physical fitness indicated in the training process. Its numerical expression is not a constant dimension, but varies depending on the qualifications of the wrestlers, their specialities, the period of the training process and the state of the organism at this time.

Strength and style of its development

“Strength”, a physical quality, is understood as the ability of a wrestler to overcome his opponent's dexterity or to resist him in the form of muscle tension.

The following types of strength are adopted: general and special, absolute and relative, fast and explosive, strength endurance.

A Common Force is a force manifested by an athlete, not referring to the special actions of a wrestler. Special strength is manifested by the athlete in special movements corresponding to the movements of the competition.

Absolute power is characterized by the power possibilities that are manifested in the movements of the athlete, which have a very large property. In wrestling, he has an important acumen for getting one-on-one with the help of force.

Relative strength, which corresponds to an athlete's 1kg weight, is an indicator of the possibility of overcoming a wrestler's personal weight. It has an important acuity in the quick execution of methods.

Rapid strength is reflected in the ability of muscles to quickly perform movements associated with overcoming relatively small external resistance.

Explosive power characterizes the ability to manifest large voltages according to its intensity in a short period of time.

Strength endurance is the ability of an athlete to show muscle tension over a relatively long period of time. To develop the strength capabilities of the wrestler, the following styles are used: repeated voltages; short-term maximum voltages; increasingly increasing weights, joint exposure; variability; styles of isometric voltages.

The technique of repeated voltages is such that the sporchi repeatedly performs exercises with weights equal to 70-80% of the maximum weight when performing the exercise “to the last breath”. This technique implies the serialization of strength training. Each series - “until the last breath”, in total 3-4 series, the rest interval between the series is 3-4 min.

One style of repeated voltages is the dynamic voltage style. It is characterized by performing exercises at a limit speed of 20-30% of the maximum weight. In this case, a large muscle strain is achieved not at the expense of weight weight, but at the expense of high-speed movement.

The short-term maximum tension style is currently the most effective for increasing muscle mutlak strength. It is intended to work with weights on the border and close to the border. In muscle training, the style of maximum voltages is manifested in exercises performed with a large weight barbell (silent, flickering couture, fast lifting, sit-ups), using one to two movements in trainers and one approach. In the training, 3-4 approaches are performed in total. The rest interval between approaches is 3-5 min.

The increasingly growing style of weights implies a gradual increase in the volume of resistance even in the next, as in a single training session.

In the first approach to training, it is recommended to start with a weight equal to 50% of the weight that an athlete can lift 10 times (10 MT). In the second approach, the exercise is performed with a weight of 75% from 10 MT, and in the third approach - with a weight of 100% from 10 MT. During the training, 3 approaches are carried out in total. The rest interval between approaches is 2-4 min. In each approach, the exercise is performed until it is clearly complete with the speed at the limit.

The percussive style is based on the percussive stimulation of muscle groups through the kinematic energy of the falling weight and the use of personal torso weight.

The fact that the muscles being trained absorb the energy of the decreasing weight contributes to the sharp transition of the muscles to the active state, the rapid development of working tension, creating the possibility of additional tension in the muscle. This ensures the intensity and agility of the next pusher movement and a quick transition from a backhand to a work that can be overcome.

As a way of applying the percussive style of developing explosive strength of the legs, one can say the deep jump exercises, which are performed with a jump to high or long, respectively. The exercise is performed from a height of 70-80 cm by falling to the ground with the foottizes slightly bent, and quickly and violently bouncing up from behind. Jumps serialized: in series 2-3, 8-10 jumps are performed in each series. The rest interval between the series is 3-5 min. The exercise is performed at most twice a week.

The style of joint influence is due to the fact that the development of the strength capabilities of the wrestler occurs directly during the performance of specialized exercises. At the same time, the strength skills and technical and tactical actions of the wrestler are developed and improved. An example of the use of a combined style of influence in wrestling is such exercises in which the wrestler improves his technical movements with an opponent of a heavier weight class.

It is very important to determine the optimal weight size. An excessive size leads to a violation of the content of movement skills, which ultimately negatively affects the technique of movement.

The variational style mainly involves performing special exercises with weights of different weights. Exercises with partners of different weights are performed in series. In a single series, 10-12 throws are first performed with a heavier weight class opponent, followed by 15-16 throws with an equal weight opponent, followed by 10-12 throws with an opponent in their weight class. In total, 3 Series will be performed. Rest interval-3-4 min. Quick-the method of variability in the development of power qualities (normative, small) is especially effective.

Improving methods with a rather heavy opponent will help develop separate power opportunities, and with an opponent in a small weight class - speed opportunities. This will ultimately lead to an increase in the result in the competition exercise.

The style of isometric muscle tension is 4-6 sec of different muscle groups. implies a continuous static maximum voltage. The value of isometric exercises is that they are not very large in size, do not take much time, are much easier to perform. In addition, with their help, it is possible to selectively influence certain muscle groups

in the appropriate oblique angles of bending or writing parts of the torso, if necessary or in circumstances.

Speed and methodology for its development.

Wrestler agility is his ability to perform certain actions and techniques in as short a period of time as possible. High results in the fight cannot be achieved without a good development of the quality of speed. A wrestler who moves quickly from his opponent to one hundredth of a second will have a significant advantage in front of him.

The agility of a wrestler largely depends on the mobility of his nerve processes, the conditions, the degree to which the sensitivity to the perception of blind changes in the opponent's movements develops in him, the skill of instantly accepting and being able to correctly cope with the situation that occurs every time in the competition, the timely and accurate execution of tactical actions.

To develop agility, the following styles are used: the technique of performing exercises in relaxed conditions. Multiple repetitions of individual movements performed with movements and great agility in relaxed conditions. For example, performing the method with a focus on agility with a partner in a small weight class. The performance of exercises in relaxed conditions encourages the execution of super-fast movements that exceed those performed in simple conditions, for example, running along a sloping path (from the mountain) is used to increase the speed of the run.

The technique of performing the exercise in weighted conditions. Many repetitions of movements performed with maximum speed in conditions that are much more difficult than those that a wrestler faces in competitions. For example, performing special exercises with a heavyweight partner.

Style of repeated voltagages. Applied in two different ways:

- performing exercises with speed on the border and around the border;
- performing the exercises in such conditions that the force pulses at the border are provided by a way of transferring a relatively light load from one place to another with great speed.

Game and competition methods are also of great importance, the use of which can be an additional motivation (incentive) for the development of agility at the expense of the emotional autonomy of the athlete, his mental state, the changing sense of competition.

To train the qualities of a wrestler's agility, exercises performed with maximum speed (they are usually called speed exercises) are used. The technique of speed exercises is obliged to ensure that they are performed at the limit speeds. The exercises must be so well studied and occupied so that the main voltagages during the execution of the exercises do not correspond to the method of execution, but to its

speed. It is necessary that the duration of the exercises is such that by the end of the performance, the speed, despite exhaustion, does not decrease.

The procedures for performing speed exercises are of great importance. The duration of each exercise is 20 sec. it should not exceed, the rest interval should be optimal, at the beginning of the repetition of the exercise, on the one hand, ensuring the recovery of the wrestler, on the other hand, the optimal mirroring of his central nervous system.

Rest at intervals should be active. To do this, various exercises are performed during breaks that do not require large voltages.

In conclusion, Judo Wrestling has evolved over the centuries, and now its prestige among mass sports is growing. This sport, which is the impetus for the maturation of many Poles, is today important in the development of physical qualities among our sports-loving youth, especially among school-age children.

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